

Assessment of Socio-Economic Factors on Performance in Economics among Secondary School Students in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

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Abstract

The study investigated “socio-economic factors on performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State”. Primary data were sourced through questionnaire from four public senior secondary schools in the study area. Three hundred and twenty-two (322) questionnaires were administered and analyzed through descriptive such as table, percentage and likert scale test were used to analyze “socio-economic factors on academic performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State”. The findings of this study revealed that on aggregate, about 49.9% and 58.4% from students and teachers strongly agreed that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, good communication system learners ability play significant role on socio-economic factors affecting performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The result of likert scale test (decision rule) of 3.2% and 3.5% rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, implying that socio-economic factors have significant impacts on academic performance of students in economics among Public Senior Secondary Schools in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. This study therefore recommends that, parents should level their economic and social support to student as such support is seen as a major contributor to students’ academic performance. The Government should formulate public-polices and plans to improve the educational facilities for the socially and economically underprivileged groups.

Keywords: Teaching-Learning, performance, socio-economics, and Secondary School.

Introduction

The students’ socio-economic background is a factor known to have a significant influence of the academic achievement of the students. According to the American psychological Association (APA), socio-economic status is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. It is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group. When viewed through a social class lens, privilege, power, and control are emphasized. Furthermore, an examination of socio-economic status as a gradient or continuous variable reveals inequities in access to and distribution of resources. Socio-economic status is relevant to all realms of behavioral and social science, including research, practice, education and advocacy (APA, 2015). Researchers have shown that the initial academic skills are correlated with the home environment, where low literacy environments and chronic stress negatively affect a child’s pre-academic skills. According to Morgan, Farkas, Hillemeier and Maczuga (2009), children from low socio-economic households and communities develop academic skills more slowly compared to children from higher socio-economic groups. Similarly, school systems in low socio-economic communities are often under resourced; a factor that negatively affect students’ academic progress (Aikens & Barbarin, 2008).

The socio-economic factors play a potential role on their children’s education, marital stability, health and nutrition value. This factor is frequently measured on the basis of the educational level, the employment status and the income of the family which determines an individual’s or a group’s social standing. The socio-economic factor is “the social standing or

class of an individual or a group”. This definition is given by the American Psychological Association (APA-2018). “The socio-economic status frequently functions as a latent variable for the academic performance of secondary education” (Bofah and Hannula, 2017). Socio-economic factor is the grouping of the attributes of the social and economic settings of an individual or a household, based on the educational attainments, the occupational status and the income of a family in the society. The socio-economic factors like that the parental educational level, their employment-status and their income level which are influencing the higher secondary school student’s academic performance. Generally, a student’s academic performance is very much influenced by different type of factors, such as the parental educational attainment-level, occupational status, family income, type of school, residential place and school environment. Hence, the settings of socio-economic factors are significantly impacting a student’s academic performance at higher secondary level education, which is an important contributing factor to a society’s economic progress.

Kumaravel et.al (2022), conducted a study on socio-economic status impact on academic performance of higher secondary students. The objective of the study is to investigate the socio-economic factor that impacted students’ academic performance at the higher secondary school level of education. The study employed multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study reveal that the educational levels of the mothers and their occupation factors considerably impact their children’s academic performance. The influence of Father’s education and employment status is on a moderate level. The income of the family has negatively impacted the students’ academic performance at 1% level significant. However, the types of schools and mediums of education also have a strong bearing on the students’ academic performance at the higher secondary level.

Idika et al (2018) investigated the determinants of Academic Achievement in Economics in Public Secondary Schools in Nsukka Local Government Area, Enugu State Nigeria. Descriptive Survey research design was adopted. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled factors affecting student’s achievement in Economics (FASAE). Four research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and four hypotheses tested at 0.5 level of significance using t test. Four factors considered in the study were teachers, students, Socioeconomic and government related factors. The sample consisted of three hundred and fifty-one research subjects (351) comprising of three hundred and twenty-seven (327) Economics students and twenty-four (24) Economics teachers. Ten schools were randomly selected out of the thirty-one (31) public secondary schools in the Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State. Findings among others revealed that the determinants of academic achievement of students in Economics were students, teachers and government related as well as the socio-economic background of parents.

The socio-economic status was positively sign of students’ academic performance in language and mathematics subjects. There is positive relationship between socio-economic factor and the students’ achievement in language and mathematical subjects of the students (Zhang et., al, 2020). Egunsola, (2014) study found that the location of the home was significant in high correlation and the academic performance of secondary students.

Poor academic achievement in Economics could be attributed to many factors among which socio-economic was considered as an important factor. This implies that Economics concepts might not be fully achieved without careful consideration of socio-economic factors. The teaching of Economics without socio-economic will certainly result in poor academic achievement. Franzer and Okebukola (2012) stressed that a professionally qualified science teacher no matter how well trained, would unable to put his ideas into practice if the school setting lacks the equipment and materials necessary for him or her to translate his competence into reality.

Educators and researchers have long been interested in exploring variables that contribute to the quality of learners. However, student outcomes are not the result of simple cause-and-effect relationships. Because education is a societal activity and no single factor can be taken in isolation as responsible for the variation in students’ academic performance. But it is a systemic interaction of complex and dynamic factors that include the characteristics of teachers and students, as well as their institutional and cultural contexts [1, 10]. Then, examining to what extent student academic performance is associated with some demographic, socio-economic, and institutional factors can be helpful to identify the main constraints and provide remedial policy options. Although several types of research have been done on this topic, most of these studies were carried out on qualitative methods in which the findings might not be representative and it would be difficult to test hypotheses. On the contrary, this study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches to analyze various factors that affect students’ academic performance. Also, there are extensive exploratory investigations regarding factors that influence students’ academic performance on a single subject. But this study gives great attention to analyzing factors contributing to students’ academic performance in all subjects.

There are extensive exploratory investigations regarding factors that influence students’ academic performance on various subjects using qualitative and quantitative approach. But this study gives great attention to analyzing social economic

factors contributing to students' academic performance in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State using descriptive and inferential statistic method of analysis.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine socio-economic factors affecting students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State
2. To determine the impacts of socio-economic factors on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Research Questions

1. What are the socio-economic factors affecting students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.
2. What is the impact of socio-economic factors on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Hypothesis

1. Socio-economic factors do not have any significant impact on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Methodology

The Study Area

Source: Adopted from Google Earth (2016)

Size and Location

Sabon Gari Local Government Area is situated in Kaduna State, North-west geopolitical zone of Nigeria with the headquarters of the LGA in the town of Sabon Gari. The study area is located between Latitude 11° 10' 15''N and between 11° 16'20''N, and longitudes 7° 39'37''E and 7° 42'45''E. The area lies within Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Nigeria with a land area of approximately 600 square kilometers. It is bounded in the North by Ikara Local Government, to Makarfi Local Government in the North-West, Giwa Local Government to the West and Zaria Local Government to the South. Sabon-Gari LGA comprises several sub-settlement, namely, Samaru, Hayin-Dogo, Bomo, Dogarawa, Zango, Palladan, Basawa, Zabi, Kwari, Barashi, Hanwa, Chikaji, and Muchia. The estimated population of Sabon Gari LGA is put at 204,562 inhabitants with the area hosting members of diverse ethnic affiliations. The Hausa language is commonly spoken in the LGA while the religions of Christianity and Islam are commonly practiced in the area. Sabon Gari LGA is a part of the Zaria Emirate.

Population of the Study

The group of people, objects, events or things that a researcher has interest in investigating is called a population (Sekaran & Bourgie, 2010). The target population of the study consists of the entire public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State, while the sample size with the population consists of four senior secondary school from SS1 to SS3 students from 2023/2024 academic session.

Research design

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive survey research design and inferential statistics in assessing socio-economic factors on performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire. Six socioeconomic factors were considered using mean and decision rule based on likert scale test of hypothesis. The six factors considered in the study were marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance, employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students, the type of school the students attended can determine the learning outcome, residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance and good communication system learners ability.

Validation of Research Instrument

The instruments were developed by the researcher and evaluated by experts from the Departments of Economics and Centre of Excellency and Research Development Federal College of Education, Zaria. Content validity was used in this investigation, a sort of validity that indicates how much the study's objectives and research questions are represented. The researchers requested experts to assess the relevance of the test items in measuring the study variables. To make the instruments better, their opinions, clarifications, and ideas were noted and effected.

Reliability of Research Instrument

Pilot study was carried out in Federal College of Education, Zaria, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Zaria Academy. The questionnaire was distributed to 100 individuals who were not part of the selected study population. A reliability index of 0.76 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test indicating that the instrument is reliable for the study. Moreso, according to Mugenda (2003) response rate above 50% is adequate enough to accomplish study objectives.

Results

Table 1 Questionnaire Distribution and Response Rate

Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Distributed questionnaires	400	100.00
Returned questionnaires	322	80.5
Retained questionnaires	78	19.5

Source: Researcher Fieldwork, 2024

Response rate

The response rate for the study was 80.5%. This shows the reliability of the results in terms of representing the study phenomenon. According to Mugenda (2003) response rate above 50% is adequate enough to accomplish study objectives. This study achieved a response rate of 80.5% hence adequate enough to establish “the determinants influencing teaching-learning and academic performance of student’s in economics in the study area. In this study, analyses were carried out using table and percentages.

Table 2. Aggregate Percentage Distribution of Sex of the respondents across the schools

Schools	Students						Teachers					
	Male		Female		Total		Male		Female		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
School A	-		33	73.0	73	22.7	49	23.3	21	18.8	70	21.7
School B	56	55.4	38	17.2	94	29.2	54	25.7	41	36.6	95	29.5
School C	45	44.6	42	19.0	87	27.0	61	29.0	22	19.6	83	25.8
School D	-	-	68	30.8	68	21.1	46	21.9	28	25.0	74	23.0
TOTAL	101	31.4	221	68.6	322	100	210	65.2	112	34.8	322	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

From table 2 out of the 400 questionnaires administered, about 22.7% of the respondents were from School A, 29.2% were from School B, while 27.0% were from School C and 21.1% were from School D. In terms of their sex distribution about 101 were males and 221 were females representing 31.4% and 68.6% respectively. All the schools under this study were male and female except School A and school D that is entirely female. In terms of percentage sex distribution of the respondents (teachers) in various schools, 21.7% of the respondents were from school D, 29.5% were from School B, while 25.8% were from School C and 23.0 were from School C. In terms of their sex distribution about 210 were males and 112 were females representing 65.2% and 34.8% respectively.

Table 3. Aggregate Percentage Distribution of age of the respondents across the schools

Schools	Students									
	10-15		15-20		20-30		30 above		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
School A	28	24.6	52	25.5	2	50.0	-	-	82	25.5
School B	30	26.3	49	24.0	1	25.0	-	-	80	24.8
School C	27	23.6	53	26.0	-	-	-	-	80	24.8
School D	29	25.4	50	24.5	1	25.0	-	-	80	24.8
TOTAL	114	35.4	204	63.4	4	1.2	-	-	322	100

Schools	Teachers									
	20-30		30-40		40-50		50 above		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
School A	8	24.2	34	27.2	26	23.0	15	29.4	83	25.8
School B	10	30.3	28	22.4	31	27.4	13	25.5	82	25.5
School C	6	18.2	31	24.8	29	25.7	11	21.6	77	23.9
School D	9	27.3	32	25.6	27	23.9	12	23.5	80	24.8
Total	33	10.2	125	38.8	113	35.1	51	15.8	322	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

From table 3, it could be observed that the highest proportion of age of the students which is 63.4% was in the age bracket of 15-20 years, followed by 10-15 years of age with 35.4%, and 1.2% of age bracket 20-30 years. In the same manner, it could be observed that the highest proportion of age of the teachers which is 38.8% was in the age bracket of 30-40 years, followed by 10-15 years of age with 35.1%, 15.8% of age bracket 50 years above and 10.2% in the age bracket of 20-30 years.

Table 4: Percentage distribution of educational qualification of the respondents (teachers) across the schools

Schools	NCE		OND/HND		B.ed/B.Sc		Masters		Others		TOTAL	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%

School A	13	25.0	-	-	40	24.2	15	28.8	14	26.4	22	6.8
School B	12	23.1	-	-	39	23.6	14	26.9	13	24.5	25	7.8
School C	12	23.1	-	-	44	26.7	12	23.1	12	22.6	23	7.1
School D	15	28.8	-	-	42	25.5	11	21.2	14	26.4	23	7.1
TOTAL	52	16.1	-	-	165	51.2	52	16.1	53	16.5	322	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

Table 4 show that most of the respondents have B.Ed. /B.Sc. which represents 51.2%, 16.5% obtained other qualification such as professional diploma in education, 16.1% obtained NCE and masters certificate respectively.

Table 5: Aggregate Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools, responses of the respondents (students) across the schools

S/N	Determinants		F	%
1.	Marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance	SA	172	53.4
		A	92	28.6
		SD	40	12.4
		D	18	5.6
		Total	322	100
2.	Employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students	SA	205	63.7
		A	93	28.9
		SD	19	5.9
		D	5	1.6
		Total	322	100
3.	Parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome	SA	145	45.3
		A	106	32.9
		SD	38	11.8
		D	33	10.2
		Total	322	100
4.	The type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome	SA	169	52.5
		A	118	36.6
		SD	21	6.5
		D	14	4.3
		Total	322	100
5.	Residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance	SA	175	54.3
		A	121	36.6
		SD	18	5.6
		D	8	2.5
		Total	322	100
6.	Good communication system learners ability	SA	116	36.0
		A	161	50.0
		SD	27	8.4
		D	18	5.6
		Total	322	100
7.	Aggregate column observation	SA	982	49.9
		A	691	35.1
		SD	198	10.1
		D	96	4.9

Researcher field survey, 2024

Table 5 shows some socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. Among such factors are; marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance, employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students, parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome, the type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome, residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance, and good communication system learners' ability. About 53.4% strongly agreed that marital stability has positive impact on teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 63.7% strongly agreed that employment status and the income of the family enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 45.3% strongly agreed that parental educational attainment-level improves teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 52.5% strongly agreed that the type of school the student attended can determine the teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 54.3% strongly agreed that residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 50.0% agree that good communication system learners ability enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. On the aggregate, about 49.9% strongly agreed that socio-economic factors that influence effective teaching-learning economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State in terms of marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system learners ability are socioeconomic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 6: Aggregate Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools, responses of the respondents (teachers) across the schools

S/N	Determinants		F	%
1.	Marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance	SA	198	61.5
		A	85	26.4
		SD	26	8.1
		D	13	4.0
		Total	322	100
2.	Employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students	SA	201	62.4
		A	106	32.9
		SD	9	2.8
		D	6	1.9
		Total	322	100
3.	Parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome	SA	175	54.3
		A	110	34.2
		SD	16	5.0
		D	21	6.5
		Total	322	100
4.	The type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome	SA	172	53.4
		A	125	38.8
		SD	18	5.6

		D	7	2.2
		Total	322	100
5.	Residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance	SA	199	61.8
		A	103	40.0
		SD	14	4.3
		D	6	1.9
		Total	322	100
6.	Good communication system learners' ability	SA	178	55.3
		A	116	36.0
		SD	17	5.3
		D	11	3.4
		Total	322	100
7.	Aggregate column observation	SA	1123	58.4
		A	645	33.5
		SD	92	4.8
		D	64	3.3
		Total	1924	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

Table6 shows the socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. Among such factors are; marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance, employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students, parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome, the type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome, residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance, and good communication system learners ability. About 61.5% strongly agreed that marital stability has positive impact on teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 62.4% strongly agreed that employment status and the income of the family enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 54.3% strongly agreed that parental educational attainment-level improves teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 53.4% strongly agreed that the type of school the student attended can determine the teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 61.8% strongly agreed that residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 55.3% agree that good communication system learners ability enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. On the aggregate, about 58.4% strongly agreed that socio-economic factors that influence effective teaching-learning economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State in terms of marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system learners ability are socioeconomic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Variab	SA	SA x 4	A	A x 3	D	D x 2	SD	SD x 1	Total = $\sum fx$	$\sum f$	Mean = $\frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$	Decision
Marital stability	172	688	92	276	18	36	40	40	1040	322	3.2	Agree
Employment status	205	820	93	279	5	10	19	19	1128	322	3.5	Strongly Agree
Parental education	145	580	106	318	33	66	38	38	1002	322	3.1	Agree
Type of school attended	169	676	118	354	14	28	21	21	1079	322	3.4	Agree
Residential places	175	700	121	363	8	16	18	18	1097	322	3.4	Agree
Good communication	116	464	161	483	18	36	27	18	1001	322	3.1	Agree
Aggregate	982	3928	691	2073	86	192	198	198	6391	1967	3.2	Agree

H₀: Socio-economic factors do not have any significant impact on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Table 7: Testing of Null Hypothesis for students: Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Source: Derived from table 5

Decision Rule

3.5 – 4.00 Strongly Agree

2.5 – 3.49 Agree

1.5 – 2.49 Disagree

1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

The result in table 7 show that on the aggregate calculated mean is 3.2 and the tabulated mean is A x 3. Since the calculated mean of 3.2 falls between the neighborhood of A x 3, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the alternative is accepted this implies that the respondent agreed that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and good communication system have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

H₀: Socio-economic factors do not have any significant impact on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Table 8: Testing of Null Hypothesis for Teachers: Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Variables	SA	SA x 4	A	A x 3	D	D x 2	SD	SD x 1	Total = $\sum fx$	$\sum f$	Mean = $\frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$	Decision
Marital stability	198	792	85	255	13	26	26	26	1099	322	3.4	Agree
Employment status	201	804	106	318	6	12	9	9	1143	322	3.5	Strongly Agree
Parental education	175	700	110	330	21	42	16	16	1088	322	3.4	Agree
Type of school attended	172	688	125	375	7	14	18	18	1095	322	3.4	Agree
Residential places	199	796	103	309	6	12	14	14	1131	322	3.5	Strongly Agree
Good communication	178	712	116	348	11	22	17	17	1099	322	3.4	Agree
Aggregate	1123	4492	645	1935	64	128	92	92	6647	1924	3.5	Strongly Agree

Source: Derived from table 6

Decision Rule

3.5 – 4.00 Strongly Agree

2.5 – 3.49 Agree

1.5 – 2.49 Disagree

1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

The result in table 8 show that on the aggregate calculated mean is 3.5 and the tabulated mean is SA x 4. Since the calculated mean of 3.5 falls between the neighborhood of SA x 4, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the alternative is accepted this implies that on the aggregate, strongly agree that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 9: Summary of descriptive statistics for students hypothesis

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Decision
1.	Marital stability	3.2	Agree
2.	Employment status	3.5	Strongly Agree
3.	Parental education	3.1	Agree
4.	Type of school attended	3.4	Agree
5	Residential places	3.4	Agree
6	Good communication	3.1	Agree
7	Aggregate	3.2	Agree

Derived from table 7

Table 9 above indicates that marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system are socio-economic factors that impacted on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 10: Summary of descriptive statistics for teachers hypothesis

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Decision
1.	Marital stability	3.4	Agree
2.	Employment status	3.5	Strongly Agree
3.	Parental education	3.4	Agree
4.	Type of school attended	3.4	Agree
5	Residential places	3.5	Strongly Agree
6	Good communication	3.4	Agree
7	Aggregate	3.5	Strongly Agree

Derived from table 8

Table 10 above indicates that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Discussion of Findings

Marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system were found to be the socioeconomic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. On the aggregate, test of hypothesis reveals that both the students and the teachers agreed and strongly agree socioeconomic factors have significant impacts on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The result of our study is consistent with the findings of Kumaravel et.al (2022), Idika et al (2018), and Hannula, 2017) who found significant relationship between socioeconomic factors such as educational levels of the mothers, occupation factors, residential places, type of school attended and students – teacher – government related factor and academic performance of the student. The income of the family has negatively impacted the students’ academic performance at 1% level as revealed by Kumaravel et.al (2022), this finding is not consistent with our finding on respondents (students and teachers) who strongly agreed that income from employment have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to examine “socio-economic factors influencing teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in selected public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State”. Socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment play significant role for effective teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in the study area. The importance of these factors in teaching and learning process in the 21st century can never be overemphasized. Socio-economic factor has a strong impact on a student’s academic performance. The socio-economic condition explores the mechanisms of student’s academic performance which are possible means for the identification of the socio-economic and cultural factors.

Recommendations

- Based on the summary of findings and the above conclusion, it is therefore recommended that;
1. Schools and teachers should make educational materials available to facilitate teaching and learning, schools and teachers should invest on human capital development to enhance mastery of the subject matter for effective teaching and learning process.

2. Parents should level their economic and social support to student as such support is seen as a major contributor to students' academic performance.
3. The Government should formulate public-policies and plans to improve the educational facilities for the socially and economically underprivileged groups.
4. The Governments educational policy should be more focused on providing cheaper, more widespread and better educational opportunities, which will help parents to reduce barriers to choices regarding sending their children to school.

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